

UNC EITs Community Engagement Tasks: Detailed Descriptions Guide

Description:

The purpose of this document is to detail the daily tasks of the EIT Project Specialists and Associate Project Specialists as they relate to their community engagement role. This document is a supplement to the Roles and Responsibilities documents and is meant to provide further clarity on roles.

Tasks:

- I. Meeting Attendance and Participation
 - a. Monthly 30 min – 1 hr meeting with Project Teams
 - i. *For projects that are onboarding:* monthly meetings will likely retain previous structure where functional teams will join to discuss data and testing
 1. In terms of community engagement, first few meetings should be focused on listening and relationship building
 - ii. *For projects in maintenance phase:* meetings will be community engagement focused and it will be at the discretion of the UNC team whether it is necessary to add a function team member to their agenda (ad hoc) or request that functional teams hold their own ad hoc meetings
 1. For description of suggested topics, please see addendum
 - iii. *For projects that are phasing out or in close out:* continue to meet with a monthly cadence until project is officially closed out. Connect with projects about how they have learned with successes and challenges and how we can share this with the rest of the consortium. Look at analyzing community engagement success and plans for sustainability of community connection
 - iv. *Non community engagement discussions* should be limited to questions about enrollment numbers/recruitment success and any ad hoc updates to REDCap dates per the Roles and Responsibilities documents
 - b. Ad-hoc project sponsored meetings (presentations, webinars, community advisory board meetings, etc)
 - i. Utilize bandwidth for community engagement focus to attend project sponsored meetings in an effort to become more 'boots on the ground' involved in community engagement strategies

Addendum

Suggested topics of conversation during monthly Project Team meetings:

- Project team members' perception of and experience with community engaged research
 - o Do they believe that community engaged research adds value to their work?
- Understand whether relationship with defined community partners is long established/leveraged based on prior collaborative work with project team members or newly formed
 - o This speaks to levels of engagement and potential sustainability
 - o Some projects do not have easily identifiable community partners and may be using a different definition of community engagement
 - o Identify methods of engagement (events, town halls, social media, etc)
 - o Understand how project teams' institution has historically interacted with the community
 - What are some procedural barriers to community partnership from the institution?
 - What are some procedural drivers to community partnerships from the institution?
- Understand social determinants of health identified in study design
 - o Identify both positive (protective) and negative (deleterious) social determinants of health
 - o Is the project team understanding and seeing social determinants of health that they had not identified or thought about prior to initiation of research (this may be anecdotal if prior to data analysis)
 - If so, has this necessitated any change in study design?
- Understand what levels of community engagement support is needed for the project
- How has required collection of Tier 1 CDEs impacted the work?
- How is the project impacting the community?
 - o What is the benefit being provided to the community partner/community?
 - o What is the burden of the study being placed on community partner/community?
- Research translation: what are the projects' plans or strategies for dissemination of research findings?
 - o Is it bi-directional with community partners?
- What are the current community needs and how can RADx-UP help to meet those needs?
- What are the project's plans for sustainability post RADx-UP funding?
 - o Will there be continued collaboration between academic institution and non-academic partners?
 - If yes, what does that look like?
 - o What are the plans for future research and/or collaboration with community partners using other funding sources?
 - o Can RADx-UP research findings be translated to other disease burdens within the target population?
 - Is the project team already doing this with other awards (supplements, parent awards, etc)
- What community engagement strategies are being employed?
 - o What is working? What is not?